

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF BIO ANALYTICAL LCMS/MS METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF SOLRIAMFETOL IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DRUGS IN RAT PLASMA

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Abstract

A simple, rapid, precise, sensitive, and reproducible reverse phase high-performance liquid chromatography LCMS/MS method has been developed for the bioanalytical analysis of Solriamfetol, using D₆-Solriamfetol as the internal standard in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Chromatographic separation of Solriamfetol was achieved using a Waters Alliance e2695 system with a Waters X-Bridge column (150x4.6 mm, 3.5 μm). The mobile phase consisted of 0.1% OPA and ACN in a 30:70% v/v ratio. The flow rate was set at 1.0 ml/min, and detection was carried out at 237 nm using a photodiode array detector at ambient temperature. The number of theoretical plates and the tailing factor for Solriamfetol were required to be not less than 2000 and not more than 2, respectively. The % relative standard deviation of peak areas for all measurements was consistently less than 2.0. The proposed method was validated according to USFDA bioanalytical guidelines and was found to be simple, economical, suitable, precise, accurate, and stable for pharmacokinetic analysis of Solriamfetol and its stability studies..

Key words: LCMS/MS, Solriamfetol, D₆– Solriamfetol, Bio analytical method, Mobile phase

1. Introduction

Solriamfetol, chemically known as (2R)-2-amino-3-phenylpropyl carbamate, has an unknown specific mechanism of action, though it may act as a dopamine and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor. It is crucial for your doctor to monitor your progress regularly to ensure the medication is working effectively and to check for any unwanted side effects. Do not use Solriamfetol in combination with carbamazepine (Tegretol®), enzalutamide (Xtandi®), mitotane (Lysodren®), oxcarbazepine (Trileptal®), phenobarbital (Luminal®), phenytoin (Dilantin®), rifampin (Rifadine®), rifapentine (Priftin®), or St. John's wort. Starting HIV medications may strengthen your immune system. Inform your doctor immediately if you or your child notice any changes in health, as the immune system might begin to fight previously hidden infections, such as pneumonia, herpes, or tuberculosis. Autoimmune disorders, including Graves' disease, polymyositis, and Guillain-Barré syndrome, may also occur

Fig 1: Chemical structure of Solriamfetol

A Literature Survey Reveals That Only A Few Analytical Methods Have Been Reported For The Quantification Of Solriamfetol Using Spectroscopy And Liquid Chromatography. There Are No Reported Bioanalytical Methods For The Estimation Of Solriamfetol. This Study Aims To Develop A Simple, Rapid, And Specific LCMS/MS Bioanalytical Method For The Estimation Of Solriamfetol In Bulk And Combined Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Equipment's: The following instruments are used to quantification of Solriamfetol by LCMS/MS.

Table I: List of Equipment's

S.No	Name	Model	Manufacturer
1.	HPLC	ALLIANCE	Waters e 2695- Empower software2.0versions
2.	LCMS/MS	QTRAP	5500 triple quadrupole
3.	pH meter	2700	Eutech
4.	Weighing balance	TE214S	Sartorius
5.	Ultra sonicator	UCA 701	Unichrome
6.	Pump	Isocratic model	--
7.	Centrifuge	R-8C	Remi
8.	Cyclomixer	CM-101	Remi

2.2 Chemicals: The following chemicals are used to quantification of Solriamfetol by LCMS/MS.

Table II: List of chemicals used in LCMS Method

S.No	Name	Grade	Manufacturer
1.	Acetonitrile	LCMS	Rankem
2.	Water (Milli Q)	LCMS	In house production
3.	OPA	LCMS	Merck
4.	Methanol	LCMS	Merck

2.3 Preparation of Solriamfetol stock solution

The stock solution of Solriamfetol used during the LCMS method development was prepared by accurately weighing the standard compound and dissolving it in acetonitrile, resulting in a concentration of 0.5 mg/ml. Appropriate dilutions with the mobile phase were made from the stock solution to prepare the working standard solutions for method development, calibration curves, and quality control (QC) samples. Both the stock solution and the working standard solutions were stored in polypropylene vials in a -20°C freezer.

2.4 LCMS / MS method development of Solriamfetol:

A robust, selective, and sensitive LCMS/MS method with UV detection was developed to quantify Solriamfetol in rat plasma. This process involved the evaluation and optimization of various parameters, including sample preparation, chromatographic separation, detection, and quantification. The steps involved in the method development are outlined below in the order they were followed:

2.5 λ_{\max} determination of Solriamfetol:

A stock solution containing 1 mg/mL of Solriamfetol was prepared by dissolving the drug in acetonitrile. This stock solution was subsequently diluted to 20 ng/mL with acetonitrile. Aliquots of this diluted solution were taken in vials and scanned for m/z using a mass detector.

Fig II: MS Spectra of Solriamfetol

2.6 Selection of the internal standard (IS) for Solriamfetol:

One of the most crucial aspects of analysis in bioanalytical methods is the use of an internal standard (IS). As a rule of thumb, a compound with structural similarity to the analyte or with significant absorbance at the detection wavelength is selected as the IS in bioanalytical LC-MS methods. Good extraction recovery and chromatographic behavior similar to the analyte are additional advantages. D6 Solriamfetol was tested for its similarity to the analyte as an IS for the Solriamfetol LC-MS method.

2.7 Optimization of the final mobile phase:

After selecting the internal standard, the mobile phase composition and buffer concentration were fine-tuned based on the retention times of Solriamfetol and the IS. The final mobile phase was chosen to ensure adequate peak separation for both Solriamfetol and the IS.

2.8 Optimization of the flow rate:

After optimizing the mobile phase composition, various flow rates were tested to ensure proper retention time, peak asymmetry, and resolution for both the drug and the internal standard (IS). Based on these experiments, the final flow rate was selected to achieve appropriate retention times, peak asymmetry, and resolution..

2.9 Extraction of Solriamfetol from plasma sample:

Plasma samples cannot be directly injected into the HPLC system for drug quantification because they can block the HPLC column, rendering it unusable. Before analysis, the drug must be extracted into a suitable solvent and then evaporated to concentrate it prior to injection into the HPLC system.

2.10 Sample extraction procedure:

2.11 Validation Bio analytical method of Solriamfetol:

A preliminary validation was conducted before initiating the final validation process to ensure that all established procedures yield the expected results.

2.11.1 System suitability:

System suitability checks are employed to verify the proper functioning of the instrument and to authorize the analysis of the next batch of samples. In chromatographic methods, these checks ensure that the system is sufficiently sensitive, specific, and reproducible for the current analytical run and throughout the study. System suitability samples were included at the beginning, middle, and end of each batch of samples. These samples were prepared to contain a final concentration of 20 ng/mL Solriamfetol and 20 ng/mL IS in the mobile phase. The relative standard deviation (RSD %) of peak area and retention time for Solriamfetol and IS were monitored over six consecutive injections to ensure they were below 2% and 5%, respectively.

2.11.2 Quality control (QC) standards:

The purpose of quality control standards (QC) is to evaluate the performance of the assay procedure across the entire calibration range. For the LC-MS method validation of GMF:

- Low Quality Control (LQC): Three times the Lower Limit of Quantification (LLOQ)
- Mid Quality Control (MQC): Approximately 100% of the highest calibration point
- High Quality Control (HQC): Approximately 150% of the highest calibration point

All QC samples were selected to ensure they were not included within the calibration point

2.11.3 Specificity and selectivity:

This test involved analyzing blank plasma samples from six different sources to detect any chromatographic interference at the retention times of Solriamfetol and the internal standard (IS).

2.11.4 Calibration curve:

An 8-point calibration curve was constructed by spiking appropriate amounts of a working solution into blank plasma to achieve final concentrations of 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, and 40 ng/mL for Solriamfetol. The calibration curve was generated by plotting the peak area ratio of Solriamfetol to the internal standard (IS) against the nominal concentrations of the calibration standards. The results were subjected to linear regression analysis. According to the acceptance criteria, each back-calculated standard concentration was required to be within $\pm 15\%$ deviation from the nominal value, except for the Lower Limit of Quantification (LLOQ), where the criterion was set at $\pm 20\%$ (as per the guidelines of the Food and Drug Administration of the United States, 2001).

2.11.5 Precision and accuracy:

Intraday precision was evaluated by analyzing six replicates each of LLOQ, LQC, MQC, and HQC samples within the same day. Reproducibility, representing interday precision, was assessed by analyzing six sets of LLOQ, LQC, MQC, and HQC samples across three different days. Intra and inter assay accuracy were determined by analyzing six replicates of each of the four QC levels (LQC, MQC, HQC, including LLOQ) on the same day and across three different days, respectively. Accuracy was calculated as the ratio of the determined concentration to the actual concentration, multiplied by 100%.

2.11.6 Recovery:

Extraction recovery of the analytes was assessed by comparing the analytical results of extracted samples at three different concentrations (LQC, MQC, HQC) in six replicates with the results of unprocessed extracted standards (representing 100% recovery). Additionally, the recovery experiment for the internal standard (IS) was conducted at a single concentration of 20 ng/mL.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Method validation for bioanalytical studies of Solriamfetol:

The method was validated to comply with the acceptance criteria outlined in industrial guidelines for bioanalytical method validation [16, 17].

3.1.1 Specificity and Selectivity:

No interfering peaks were detected in six different random blank rat plasma samples at the retention times of either Solriamfetol or the internal standard (IS). As observed from the chromatogram, the total run time was 10 minutes, with the retention times of the drug and IS

approximately at 5.011 and 5.014 minutes, respectively. In the chromatogram of blank plasma, there were no interfering peaks near the peaks corresponding to Solriamfetol and IS. This observation was similarly noted in the chromatogram of blank plasma spiked with IS.

Fig III:Chromatogram of Blank Plasma

Fig IV:Blank plasma spiked with IS

Fig V: Blank plasma spiked with analyte at LLOQ

3.1.2 System suitability:

The %RSD for the Solriamfetol and IS area ratio was determined to be 0.61% and 0.46%, respectively, indicating that the system suitability criteria were met..

Table III: System suitability Results of Solriamfetol

Sample Name	Analyte Area	Analyte RT(min)	ISTD Area	ISTD RT (min)	Area Ratio
MQC	2.5729x10 ⁵	5.006	2.5896x10 ⁵	5.002	0.9634
MQC	2.5429x10 ⁵	5.011	2.5462x10 ⁵	5.019	0.9672
MQC	2.5989x10 ⁵	5.014	2.5953x10 ⁵	5.017	0.9698
MQC	2.5619x10 ⁵	5.017	2.5642x10 ⁵	5.018	0.9677
MQC	2.5669x10 ⁵	5.021	2.5841x10 ⁵	5.021	0.9632
MQC	2.5589x10 ⁵	5.013	2.5952x10 ⁵	5.017	0.9573
Mean	2.5671x10 ⁵	5.093	2.5791x10 ⁵	5.016	0.9648
SD	0.0186	0.0053	0.0198	0.00686	0.00447
%RSD	0.61	0.10	0.62	0.14	0.46

Acceptance Criteria: The % RSD of the retention time (RT) should be ≤ 2.00 %. The % RSD of the area ratio should be ≤ 5.00 %.

Fig VI: Chromatogram of system suitability

3.1.3 Sensitivity:

The %RSD for Solriamfetol was found to 0.30%. Hence it passed the sensitivity.

Table IV:Sensitivity Results of Solriamfetol

Replicate Number	LLOQ
	Nominal Concentration(ng/ml)
	1.1559
	Nominal Concentration Range(ng/ml)
	(1.1585-1.1596)
Calculated Concentration(μ g/ml)	
1	1.1598
2	1.1507
3	1.1548
4	1.1556
5	1.1596
6	1.1548
N	6
Mean	1.1559
SD	0.00342
%RSD	0.30
% Mean Accuracy	98.89%

Acceptance Criteria: At least 67 % (4 out of 6) of samples should be within 80.00-120.00 % Mean accuracy should be within 80.00-120.00 %. %RSD accuracy should be \leq 20.00 %.

3.1.4 Linearity:

The standard curves showed linearity across the concentration range of 2.0-40.00 ng/mL for Solriamfetol, with a mean correlation coefficient of 0.999. Quantification of samples was performed using the ratio of peak area of the analyte to that of the internal standard (IS). These peak area ratios were plotted against plasma concentrations.

Table V: Preparation of Solriamfetol working stock solution for standard curve

Linearity	Plasma (μl)	ACN (μl)	Std Stock (μl)	IS (μl)	MP added (μl)	Solriamfetol Conc. (ng/ml)	Solr response	Area res ratio
Linearity-1	200	300	50	500	1450	2.00	0.364	0.116
Linearity-2	200	300	125	500	1375	5.00	0.742	0.235
Linearity-3	200	300	250	500	1250	10.00	1.533	0.491
Linearity-4	200	300	375	500	1125	15.00	2.186	0.699
Linearity-5	200	300	500	500	1000	20.00	3.064	0.979
Linearity-6	200	300	625	500	875	25.00	3.774	1.204
Linearity-7	200	300	750	500	750	30.00	4.456	1.425
Linearity-8	200	300	1000	500	500	40.00	6.057	1.940
SLOPE						0.0466		
INTERCEPT						0.02055		
r square						0.99942		

Acceptance Criteria: The Linearity Regression coefficient should be $R^2 = 0.999$

Fig VII: Calibration plot for concentration v/s Area ratio of Solriamfetol

3.1.5 LOD and LOQ:

The limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) for Solriamfetol were determined using the calibration curve method. The LOD for Solriamfetol was found to be 0.27 μg/mL, with a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) value of 4. The LOQ for Solriamfetol was determined to be 2.7 μg/mL, with a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) value of 24.

Table VI: LOD and LOQ data for Solriamfetol

Name	LOD		LOQ	
	Concentration (ng/ml)	s/n	Concentration (ng/ml)	s/n
Solriamfetol	0.27	4	2.7	24

3.1.6 Precision and accuracy:

Intra-assay precision and accuracy were assessed by analyzing six replicates at six different QC levels containing Solriamfetol. Inter-assay precision was evaluated by analyzing QC samples at four levels across four separate runs. Acceptance criteria for the data included: Accuracy within 85–115% of the actual values for all QC levels, with the exception of LLQC (Lowest Level Quality Control), where accuracy should be within 80–120%. Precision within $\pm 15\%$ relative standard deviation (RSD) for all QC levels, and $< 20\%$ RSD for LLQC.

Table VII: Accuracy and precision of data of the Solriamfetol (n= 6)

Quality control sample	Spiked concentration (ng/ml)	Mean (ng/ml)	SD	Accuracy (%)	%RSD
Intra-day					
LLOQ	1.1598	1.1585	0.0013	96.32	0.82
LQC	10.209	10.235	0.0244	98.28	0.16
MQC	20.113	20.1763	0.0987	100.05	0.33
HQC	30.385	30.3840	0.0375	99.89	0.08

Acceptance Criteria: The within- and between-batch precision for LQC, MQC, and HQC samples should be $\leq 15.00\%$. For the LLOQ QC, the precision should be $\leq 20.00\%$.

3.1.7 Recovery of analyte:

The recovery of the drug and IS was evaluated at three concentration levels: low, medium, and high quality control. Recovery was calculated by comparing the response in replicate samples with that of neat standard solution responses. For Solriamfetol, the recovery ranged from 95.1% to 99.8%, while for the IS, it ranged from 94.25% to ...

Table VIII: Recovery of analyte of Solriamfetol

Replicate Number	HQC		MQC		LQC	
	Extracted Response	Un Extracted Response	Extracted Response	Un Extracted Response	Extracted Response	Un Extracted Response
1	3.362x10 ⁵	3.969x10 ⁵	2.415x10 ⁵	2.858x10 ⁵	1.215 x10 ⁵	1.761x10 ⁵
2	3.365x10 ⁵	3.945x10 ⁵	2.458x10 ⁵	2.825x10 ⁵	1.214x10 ⁵	1.787x10 ⁵
3	3.425x10 ⁵	3.925x10 ⁵	2.369x10 ⁵	2.847x10 ⁵	1.253x10 ⁵	1.723x10 ⁵
4	3.345x10 ⁵	3.945x10 ⁵	2.487x10 ⁵	2.869x10 ⁵	1.263x10 ⁵	1.741x10 ⁵
5	3.432x10 ⁵	3.969x10 ⁵	2.341x10 ⁵	2.873x10 ⁵	1.259x10 ⁵	1.721x10 ⁵
6	3.397x10 ⁵	3.981x10 ⁵	2.462x10 ⁵	2.883x10 ⁵	1.254x10 ⁵	1.743x10 ⁵
N	6	6	6	6	6	6
Mean	3.3877x10 ⁵	3.9223x10 ⁵	2.4220x10 ⁵	2.8258x10 ⁵	1.2097x10 ⁵	1.7127x10 ⁵
SD	0.0359	0.0394	0.0575	0.1108	0.0708	0.1173
%RSD	0.08	0.09	0.19	0.35	0.59	0.71
%Mean Recovery	98.12	99.89%	99.12%	100.18%	96.54%	99.63%
Overall % Mean Recovery	98.99%					
Overall SD	1.1604					
Overall %RSD	0.43					

Acceptance Criteria: The %RSD of recovery at each QC level and for ISTD should be ≤ 15.00 %. The overall mean recovery %RSD for all QC levels should be ≤ 20.00 %.

4. Conclusion

In these studies, experiments were conducted on Solriamfetol using HPLC and LC-MS/MS coupled with a PDA detector. HPLC LC-MS/MS instruments are widely available in analytical laboratories due to their cost-effectiveness. While protein precipitation and solid extraction methods have been previously used in published literature, we have developed a liquid-liquid extraction method for sample preparation, which offers increased sensitivity and extends column life compared to protein precipitation methods. Solid phase extraction was avoided due to its higher cost. Various parameters for these techniques were carefully selected after thorough justification and multiple trial and error experiments. The HPLC method developed for Solriamfetol analysis in plasma is highly specific and sensitive. The methods established in our laboratory are straightforward, utilizing a liquid-liquid extraction procedure, which enhances throughput for analysis. All validation data met the acceptance criteria outlined in the US FDA guidelines.

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